

complexes are coordinated through both thiocarbonyl sulphur and the nitrogen atom of the ligand. This indicates that Rh and Ru form an inner complex type structure. The reflectance spectra of the complexes was also examined. Both the complexes were found to be insoluble in water and most of the organic solvents. Thus on the basis of analytical, infrared, magnetic moment and reflectance data octahedral configuration have been proposed for the rhodium and ruthenium (III) complexes.

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References

1. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, 35, 150.
2. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *Science and Culture*, 1973, 39, 345.
3. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 158.
4. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 227.
5. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 912.
6. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *Labdev, J. Sci. Tech.*, 1973, 11-A, 44.
7. A. K. NIGAM and G. D. TIWARI, *Science and Culture*, 1976, 42, 265.
8. M. E. BAGULEY and J. A. ELVIDGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 709.

Thiomalate Complexes of Some Divalent Metal Ions

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IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on thiomalate complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III), we report in this paper the results of our studies on the interaction of Be(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with thiomalic acid by pH titration method.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the investigations were of AnalaR grade. The metals were estimated gravimetrically from their respective salt solutions by standard methods. Ionic strength of 0.1M was maintained by the addition of suitable quantity of NaClO₄ to the

solutions. All experiments were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere using a Marconi pH meter. pH titration of 50 ml of solutions containing metal salt and thiomalic acid in different proportions against 0.1 M NaOH were performed at 31°±0.5°.

pH titration of 50 ml of solutions containing 0.005 gm moles of NaClO₄ and

A — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid

B₁ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of MnSO₄

B₂ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of Co(ClO₄)₂

B₃ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of NiSO₄

B₄ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of ZnSO₄

B₅ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of Be(ClO₄)₂

against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide.

Results and Discussion

The amount of acid liberated during complex formation between M²⁺ ions (where M=Be, Mn, Co, Ni and Zn) and thiomalic acid, remains the same even if the metal to ligand ratio is increased from 1 : 1.25 to 1 : 5 which indicates the formation of 1 : 1 type of complex. The reaction taking place due to the interaction of these divalent metal ions with thiomalic acid can be represented as

$$\text{Hence, } K = \frac{[C][H^+]^n}{[M^{2+}][H_3TML]} \quad \dots (2)$$

It can be shown as in the citrate complex of cadmium²

and yttrium³ and malate complex of yttrium⁴ that,

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TTML}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - a/b \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{Where, } a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$$\text{and } b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A$; $\Delta[\text{TTML}] = [\text{TTML}]_B - [\text{TTML}]_A$; $[\text{NaOH}]_A$, $[\text{NaOH}]_B$, $[\text{TTML}]_A$, $[\text{TTML}]_B$, $[\text{C}]$ and n are represented by molar concentrations of sodium hydroxide at Curve A and B, total thiomalate concentration at Curve A and B, thiomalate complex and the number of protons liberated per gm. atom of metal ion respectively. k_1 (2.291×10^{-4}), k_2 (2.291×10^{-5}) and k_3 (4.266×10^{-11}) are the first, second and third dissociation constants⁵ of thiomalic acid respectively.

When the formation of the complex is complete, $[\text{C}] = [\text{Metal Salt}]$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TTML}]}{[\text{Metal Salt}]} = n - a/b \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $-\Delta[\text{TTML}]$, $[\text{Metal salt}]$ and then n were calculated at different pH values by the methods adopted earlier. The values of n are found to be less than 2 below pH 4.6, 5.8, 5.0, 4.8 and 4.6 for beryllium, manganese, cobalt, nickel and zinc respectively. Hence below these pH values a neutral complex C is formed in each case with liberation of two protons according to the equation

The concentration of complex C was calculated below these pH values by assuming n values to be 2, by the equation (4) and K values were calculated as before by the equation (2). The mean values of $-\log K$ are found to be 5.17 ± 0.11 , 5.91 ± 0.05 , 5.84 ± 0.09 , 5.48 ± 0.11 and 4.28 ± 0.16 for beryllium, manganese, cobalt, nickel and zinc thiomalate system respectively. The values of n are greater than 2 and less than 3 at and above pH 4.6, 5.8, 4.8 and 4.6 for beryllium, manganese, nickel and zinc respectively. Hence this indicates the dissociation of the neutral complex C, according to the equation (5)

The equilibrium constant K_1 can be represented by the equation (6)

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} \quad \dots (6)$$

It can be shown as in the case of cadmium citrate

complex² that

$$K_1 = \frac{(n-2)[\text{H}^+]}{(3-n)} \quad \dots (7)$$

The values of K_1 are calculated by equation (7) and the mean values of $-\log K_1$ are found to be 4.82 ± 0.15 , 7.48 ± 0.24 , 5.38 ± 0.15 and 5.10 ± 0.06 for beryllium, manganese, nickel and zinc respectively.

The results indicate that the stabilities of the thiomalate complexes of divalent metal ions studied in the present investigation decrease in the order $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$ which is in agreement with the observations⁴⁻⁷ made by earlier workers.

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References

1. N. K. MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
2. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
3. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Acta. Chim. Hung.*, 1973, 79, 279.
4. N. K. MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 337.
5. G. R. LENZ and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 378.
6. G. E. CHENEY, Q. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 2055.
7. W. MANCH and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, 38, 192.
8. W. STRICKS, I. M. KOLTHOFF and A. HEYNDRIK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1515.

Some Anionic Complexes of Organometal (III) Derivatives

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A few physico-chemical studies such as electrophoresis anion exchange, paper chromatography have been reported^{1,2} to indicate complexation between organothallium(III) cations and tetraalkyl-ammonium salts. Some organothallium complexes of the general formula $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{PhTlX}_3]$ and $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{PhTlX}_4]$ have also been isolated in the solid state³. Corresponding anions of organometal(III) containing mixed halo-and halo-pseudohalo are not known. This investigation for the first time reports the synthesis and characterisation of such anionic complexes of the formula $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{R}_2\text{MXX}']$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et, Bu}$; $\text{R}' = \text{Ph or Bu}$; $\text{X and X}' = \text{Cl, Br, I, N}_3 \text{ or NCSe}$).